

SELF-EFFICACY ON ANXIETY LEVELS IN FACING OF COMPETENCY TESTS FOR STUDENTS OF THE NURSE PROFESSION

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Abstract

Self-efficacy is an individual's belief in ability. Self-efficacy plays an important role in many aspects of life, including education, work, health, and interpersonal relationships. Individuals with high self-efficacy tend to be more motivated, try harder, and are more resistant to stress and failure. Anxiety is an emotional response to a perceived threat, which can be tangible. Anxiety is often characterized by feelings of fear, worry, and tension, and can be accompanied by physical symptoms such as increased heart rate, excessive sweating, and shortness of breath. The purpose of this study is to determine the relationship between self-efficacy and anxiety levels in facing the competency test in Nurse Professional Students of Faletehan University in 2024. The method used is quantitative through a cross sectional design approach. The population of this study is 135 respondents with the number of samples determined by the Total Sampling Technique of 135 students. The results and analysis through the chi-square test obtained univariate results showed that (51.1%) respondents had high self-efficacy and (48.9%) had low self-efficacy. Meanwhile, students who are not anxious (51.9%) and students who are anxious (48.1%). The results of this bivariate analysis obtained a p-value of 0.032, at $\alpha=0.005$ ($p \leq \alpha$) In conclusion, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship. It is hoped that nursing students can further improve their self-efficacy so that they can be more confident when taking the exam.

Keywords: *Self-Efficacy, Anxiety, Students, Nurses, Competency Test,*

1. INTRODUCTION

UU No. 53 of 2023 years, concerning Higher Education Quality Assurance, explains that higher education quality assurance is a systemic activity to improve the quality of higher education in a planned and sustainable manner. In the field of health, the government has organized higher education in the health sector, one of which is a competency test, at this stage students will have graduation competency standards, namely regarding the unity of competence in attitudes, skills, and knowledge that show student achievement from the results of their learning at the end of the higher education program in the field of health workers.

Health workers play a very important role in life in providing health services in the community, as well as ensuring community welfare in health as stated in the law (No. 17 of 2023). According to the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia (2019), a health worker is defined as someone who is devoted to the health sector who has knowledge and skills and education in the health sector that requires the authority to make

efforts in the health sector. So that to become competent and professional health workers, it is necessary to conduct a competency test nationally, namely the Competency Test.

Nurse professional students must achieve learning in the nurse profession education program, which consists of several aspects, namely attitude, mastery, knowledge, authority and responsibility, general skills, and special skills [3]. The implementation of the competency test is increasingly felt to be a burden, especially for nursing students who if they do not graduate, cannot attend graduation ceremonies and are not registered as nurses. This causes worry, fear, tension, and anxiety due to fear of not passing the competency test and not being able to work without STR [15].

A person who is experiencing an anxiety disorder will usually feel anxious, afraid to make decisions, strange thinking that is delusional, and can end up isolating and isolating themselves. Anxiety disorders can also have physical effects such as rapid heart rate, tremors, fatigue, dizziness, difficulty concentrating, nausea, and sleep disturbances [12]. Basic Health Research (RisKesDas) in 2018, shows problems with anxiety, mental, emotional, depression, and anxiety disorders in the young age group of 15-24 years with a total of 10% who experience problems with anxiety, mental, emotional, depression and anxiety disorders. [7], states that anxiety that occurs in a person provides an adaptive or health response, when a person views anxiety in an adaptive way, the response that occurs will be anticipated. At the same time, a person who is unable to adapt to the anxiety he or she experiences will give a maladaptive response. Health responses can occur in four levels of anxiety starting from mild anxiety, moderate anxiety, severe anxiety, to the final stage of anxiety, namely panic.

Anxiety can affect the results that students will get, especially moderate anxiety to panic. The higher the level of anxiety, the more important it is for individuals to use coping mechanisms to cope with that anxiety. When students experience anxiety, individuals will use various coping mechanisms to overcome anxiety such as individual abilities, social support, material assets, and positive individual beliefs [2].

Students can do several ways to overcome anxiety, one of which is to increase self-efficacy in students, according to [9], self-efficacy is a healthy confidence in one's own potential who believes that he is capable of doing an activity so that he can produce positive things and achieve the expected goals. Self-efficacy is divided into three, namely, magnitude, *generality*, and strength. Students who have high self-efficacy will have high confidence and can control the results of their efforts to prepare for the exam.

Low self-efficacy will increase anxiety and avoidant behavior because a person who does not have confidence that he or she cannot cope with the problems that will arise. Therefore, high self-efficacy will have a positive impact on individuals to face the demands of existing tasks, so students need to increase self-efficacy [22]. Faletihan University is one of the health campuses in the Banten area, which consists of several faculties, one of which is the Faculty of Health Sciences. Faletihan University also has several study programs, one of which is the Nurse Profession program which has been taking the competency test since 2016, based on the results of interviews with the head of the Faletihan University study program, often get a competency test score above 90% in each exam period, because before taking the exam, students are often equipped with preparations before facing the competency test. But of course, the preparation he made was never separated from the student's concern about the results that he did not expect in the results of the National Competency Test. Based on the phenomenon described above, the researcher is interested in conducting research on the

Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Anxiety Levels in Facing the Competency Test in Nursing Professional Students at Faletahan University in 2024.

2. METHODOLOGY

This study used a type of quantitative research with *Design Cross Sectional*, which aims to find out between independent variables and dependent variables. This study analyzed the relationship between self-efficacy and anxiety levels in facing competency tests in nursing professional students of Faletahan University. This research has been submitted to the Health Research Ethics Committee of Faletahan University and was declared to have passed the research ethics test with Ethical Clearance Number No. 151/KEPK. UF/V/2024 which was issued on May 13, 2024. The implementation of the research was carried out at the end of May 2024 at Faletahan University by involving a population of 135 students of the Faletahan University Nurse Profession with a sampling technique using total sampling, namely the total number of the existing population, namely 135 people. Data analysis in this study uses *the chi-square test*.

3. RESULTS

Table 1: Frequency Distribution of Characteristics (Age, Gender, GPA, Work Status, Marital Status, Study Activeness) Faletahan University in 2024

Characteristic	f	Percentage (%)
Age		
21-22 Years	24	17,8 %
23-24 Years	106	78,5 %
25-27 Years	5	3,7 %
Total	135	100,0 %
Gender		
Man	38	28,1 %
Woman	97	71,9 %
Total	135	100,0 %
GPA		
1.00-2.00 (Low)	4	3,0 %
3.00-4.00 (High)	131	97,0 %
Total	135	100,0 %
Work Status		
Work	10	7,4 %
Not Working	125	92,6 %
Total	135	100,0 %
Marital Status		
Marry	9	6,7 %
Not Married	126	93,3 %
Total	135	100,0 %
Study Activeness	135	100,0 %

Table 1, shows that the majority of nursing students aged 23-24 years as many as 106 respondents with a percentage (78.5%) this age is a fairly productive age based on this category, the age of the respondents is in the transition period from university to the world of work. The age of 18 to 25 years is the period when cognitive abilities such as memory,

problem-solving, and creativity are at their peak. Students in this age range are usually able to process information quickly and efficiently, and are essential for academic success.

In terms of gender characteristics, most of the nursing profession students are female as many as 97 respondents with a percentage (71.9%), while male as many as 38 respondents with a percentage (28.1%) historically, the nursing profession is dominated by women, probably because women are considered to have a higher level of perseverance compared to men. In terms of nursing education programs, it may be more attractive to women because of the social perception and support they receive from their families and communities. Educational institutions may also have more female enrollees than men in nursing programs [4].

Based on the GPA value, namely with a GPA value of 3.00-4.00 (High) totaling 131 respondents with a percentage (97.0%) this percentage is greater when compared to the GPA value of 1.00-2.00 (Low), namely 4 Respondents with a percentage (3.0%) so that there are still many students who have high scores. This is important because their success is highly anticipated by the community to improve nursing and health services. A high GPA reflects the results of the entire learning process, where students who have high motivation to learn and are diligent both cognitively, affectively, and psychomotor will master the concept of nursing. As stated by [1], students with a good GPA in the final phase of learning will find it easier to understand and remember the concepts or theories that have been obtained, so that their intellectual and technical abilities increase

Table 1, also shows that from the aspect of job status, most of the nursing students are not working as many as 125 respondents with a percentage (92.6%), while those who work as many as 10 respondents with a percentage (7.4%). Based on marital status, most of the unmarried students were 126 respondents with a percentage (93.3%), and married students were 9 respondents with a percentage (6.7%). Based on the learning activity of all active nurse students as many as 135 respondents with a percentage (100.0%), student activity in learning is very important to achieve optimal learning achievement. Students who are active in learning and have high motivation tend to achieve better learning achievements.

And based on marital status, it shows that of the 135 respondents studied, there are 9 respondents who are married with a percentage (6.7%), and unmarried students, which is 126 respondents with a percentage (93.3%) of 135 students. All respondents in this study were active in debriefing for UKOM, namely 135 respondents with a percentage (100.0%).

Table 2: *Distribution of Self-Efficacy frequencies in Nurse Profession students at Faletahan University in 2024*

Self-Efficacy	f	Percentage (%)
Low, if < 62 (Median)	66	48,9 %
High, if ≥ 62 (Median)	69	51,1 %
Total	135	100,0 %

The results of the study in table 2 show that of the total 135 respondents studied, most of the respondents had high self-efficacy, namely 69 respondents (51.1%), while almost most of the respondents, namely 66 (48.9%) felt that their self-efficacy was low. From the results of

the above study, it is shown in detail that as many as 135 nursing professional students with 20 items of instrument statements, most of them chose the answer Yes with 66.7% choosing the statement that they are confident that they can do difficult nursing actions, namely by the way students find ways and explore more their abilities so they are confident to do the nursing action, So that their abilities will increase. Then most of the respondents (69.6%) said that students felt confident in the opinions they would submit during discussions with lecturers and clinic supervisors. The expression of opinions is an important ability in various contexts, including in academic, professional, and social environments, because everyone has the right to have or express opinions that will affect their confidence level [16].

This study shows that self-efficacy in facing exams in Nurse students is influenced by a combination of experience, social support, learning strategies, material understanding, and the ability to manage stress. Increasing self-efficacy can help students to be better prepared for exams, reduce anxiety, and improve their academic performance. This study is in line with [19], stating that the majority of Tanjungpura University nursing students class of 2020 have a high level of self-efficacy. According to [10], one of the main factors that can increase self-efficacy is one's personal experience.

Table 3: Frequency distribution of Anxiety Levels among Nurse Profession students at Faletahan University in 2024

Anxiety Level	f	Percentage (%)
Anxious	66	48,1 %
No Anxiety	69	51,9 %
Total	135	100,0 %

Based on table 3, it shows that of the 135 respondents studied, most of the respondents felt unanxious as many as 70 respondents (51.9%), while almost most of the respondents felt anxious as many as 65 (48.1%). According to *the American Psychological Association (APA)* in [20], anxiety is an emotional state that arises when an individual is stressed, characterized by feelings of tension, thoughts that give rise to worry, and is accompanied by physical symptoms such as increased heart rate, increased blood pressure, and other physical symptoms.

Based on the results of the study, it shows that almost some of the nursing students are in the category of not anxious (51.9%), and almost some who experience anxiety (48.1%) this anxiety can motivate learning, help find the right solution to problems, and increase creativity. Based on the results of this study, it is described in detail through filling out a questionnaire by respondents that almost most of the respondents (71.1%) students have hope for their future so that nursing students are active in participating in learning, debriefing and preparing themselves to take the competency test that they will face. Thus, students who have prepared themselves before the implementation of the competency test can be more confident and not feel anxious when carrying out the competency test. Hope is the waiting to achieve a goal in the future that is influenced by the importance of the goal to the individual and encourages the individual to act to achieve it [5].

The results of this study also found the fact that there are still some nursing students who experience anxiety (48.1%), this can be seen from the results of the answers to the anxiety questionnaire that has been filled out by the respondents where the respondents cannot feel positive feelings at all (42.2%), high levels of stress and anxiety can obscure a positive view.

Students who are stressed or anxious often experience negative thoughts and find it difficult to enjoy things that would normally provide satisfaction or happiness. However, excessive and negative anxiety can be detrimental, as well as disrupting the physical and psychological condition of the individual [18].

Table 4: *The Relationship between Self-Efficacy and Anxiety Levels in Facing the Competency Test in Faletahan University Nurse Professional Students in 2024*

Self-efficacy	Anxiety levels				N	Total	P-value	OR (CI 95%)
	Anxious		No anxiety					
	N	%	N	%				
Low	38	57,6	28	42,4	66	100		
Tall	27	39,1	42	60,6	69	100	0,032	2,11
Total	65	48,1	70	45,8	135	100		

The results of the analysis of the relationship between self-efficacy and the level of anxiety of nursing students in facing the competency test at Faletahan University showed that almost all students had high self-efficacy, which was 69 (69.0%). From the results of the statistical test, a significant value of $p\text{-value} = 0.032 < \alpha = 0.005$ was obtained. Therefore, it can be concluded that there is a significant relationship between self-efficacy and anxiety levels in nursing students.

Based on the results of cross-tabulation it was found that 66 respondents with low self-efficacy, 69 (51.1%) had high self-efficacy, while for anxiety tabulations students who experienced anxiety were 65 (48.1%), and students who were not anxious were 70 (51.9%). This is in line with the theory [9], explaining self-efficacy is the feeling of having the ability to perform activities that require confidence and self-confidence. Students who have high self-efficacy see assignments as challenges to be conquered, and if they fail, they will try harder. In contrast, students with low self-efficacy see assignments as difficult, which can cause them to feel anxious and stressed.

This study was strengthened by [17] in his research which showed that there was a significant relationship between self-efficacy and anxiety level with the results of statistical tests obtaining $p\text{-values} < 0.05$. The results of the research show that the self-efficacy possessed by nurse professional students in facing the competency test almost all of the students have high self-efficacy. Because almost all nursing students can control this anxiety, their self-efficacy is high. High self-efficacy can be caused by the high way of thinking of nursing students, having high confidence, being able to control anxiety, and fear as well as nursing students and being active in providing debriefing for competency tests.

The results of this study can be seen that nursing students have high self-efficacy and most of them do not experience anxiety and a small part feel anxious when they are going to face the exam based on the results of the questionnaire. The positive impact of this anxiety is to encourage students to develop positive coping mechanisms, such as discussing with their supervisors to reduce their anxiety [18].

4. CONCLUSIONS

The results of this study show that most of the professional students are on average productive age 23-24 years old, the average female professional students are 97 respondents (71.9%), the majority of respondents are not working, the average is not married. The results

of the study in table 5.2 show that of the total 135 respondents studied, most of the respondents had high self-efficacy, namely 69 respondents (51.1%),

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